

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

18 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 18, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 18, ISSUE 1

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УДК: 618.11–006.2–031.14–008.06

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NEW TREATMENT OPPORTUNITIES FOR POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME

For citation: Agababyan Larisa Rubenovna, Usmankulova Habiba Mizrobjonovna. New treatment opportunities for polycystic ovary syndrome // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2025, vol. 10, issue 1, pp.59-65

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15007803>

ANNOTATION

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a heterogeneous complex disorder characterized by oligo-anovulation, hyperandrogenism and/or hyperandrogenemia, and polycystic ovarian morphological changes. Interest in PCOS encompasses several specific aspects, including reproductive, cosmetic, and medical aspects

Key words: polycystic ovary syndrome, etiology, treatment, myoinositol, ovulation induction, drills, oral combined contraceptives, life style changes.

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НОВЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ СИНДРОМА ПОЛИКИСТОЗНЫХ ЯИЧНИКОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Синдром поликистозных яичников (СПКЯ) представляет собой гетерогенное комплексное нарушение, характеризующееся олиго-ановуляцией, гиперандрогенизмом и/или гиперандрогемией, а также поликистозными морфологическими изменениями яичников. Интерес к СПКЯ охватывает несколько специфических аспектов, включая репродуктивные, косметические и медицинские

Ключевые слова: СПЯ, этиология, лечение, миоинозитол, индукция овуляции, слюнотечение, комбинированные оральные контрацептивы, модификация образа жизни.

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TUXUMDON POLIKISTOZ SINDROMINI DAVOLASHNING YANGI IMKONIYATLARI**ANNOTATSIYA**

Tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi (PCOS) oligo-anovulyatsiya, giperandrogenizm va/yoki gipreandrogenemiya, shuningdek, tuxumdonlardagi polikistik morfologik o'zgarishlar bilan tavsiflangan geterogen murakkab kasallikdir. TPS ga bo'lgan qiziqish reproduktiv, kosmetik va tibbiy jihatlarni o'z ichiga olgan bir qancha o'ziga xos jihatlarni qamrab oladi

Kalit so'zlar: Tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi, patogenezi, davolash, mio-inositol, ovulyatsiya induksiyasi, drilling, turmush tarzini o'zgartirish.

Tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi reproduktiv yoshdagi ayollarda eng keng tarqalgan endokrin kasallik bo'lib, reproduktiv va metabolik kasalliklar bilan tavsiflanadi. Psixologik muammolar, gipotalamus-gipofiz tizimining disfunktsiyasi, tuxumdon disfunktsiyasi, mitoxondriyal disfunktsiya, semizlik va D vitamini etishmovchiligi TPS bo'lgan ayollarda bepustlikning etiologiyasi sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Ko'rib chiqish kasallikning patogenezi va uni davolashga yondashuvlar, shu jumladan ratsional ovqatlanish, kombinatsiyalangan gormonal kontratseptivlar bo'yicha so'nggi tadqiqotlarni ko'rib chiqilgan, klomifen sitrat bilan ovulyatsiyani induksiya qilish va yordamchi reproduktiv texnologiyalar tuxumdon polikistoz sindromini davolashda umumiy qabul qilingan yondashuvlar sifatida belgilangan. [1].

Tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi patogenezi haqida yangilik

Tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi (PCOS) murakkab endokrin kasallik bo'lib, u nafaqat reproduktiv, balki metabolik kasalliklar bilan ham namoyon bo'ladi. Ushbu kasallik reproduktiv yoshdagi ayollarning katta qismiga ta'sir qiladi va ularning salomatligi uchun jiddiy oqibatlariga olib kelishi mumkin. Tuxumdon polikistoz sindromining asosiy ko'rinishlariga tartibsiz hayz ko'rish, bepustlik, shuningdek, tana va yuzda ortiqcha soch o'sishi (girsutizm), akne va seboreik dermatit kabi giperandrogeniya belgilari kiradi.

Tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi patogenezi tug'ilishga ta'sir qiluvchi bir nechta asosiy omillarni aniqlaydi. Depressiya va tashvish kabi bemorlarning psixologik muammolari kasallikning namoyon bo'lishini kuchaytirishi va davolanishni qiyinlashtirishi mumkin. Gipotalamus-gipofiz disfunktsiyasi ham muhim rol o'ynaydi, bu esa hayz davrining normal tartibga solinishiga olib keladi. Bundan tashqari, tuxumdonlar va mitoxondriyalarning disfunktsiyasi tuxumlarning sifatini va urug'lantirish qobiliyatini buzishi mumkin.

Tuxumdon polikistoz sindromining xarakterli belgilaridan biri bu sindromning ko'plab fenotipik xususiyatlarini aniqlaydigan ortiqcha androgenlardir. 2020 yilda bir qator tadqiqotlar natijalari e'lon qilindi, ular metabolizmdagi o'zgarishlar tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi biologik mexanizmlarining asosini tashkil etishini ko'rsatdi. Ushbu kashfiyot metabolik gomeostaz va reproduktiv funktsiya o'rtasidagi murakkab o'zaro ta'sirlarni tushunishni sezilarli darajada kengaytirdi. Masalan, M. Dapas va boshqalarning ishi. reproduktiv va metabolik xususiyatlarda farq qiluvchi genetik jihatdan turli xil tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi subtiplari mavjudligini ko'rsatdi.

Yy tadqiqoti. Joo va boshqalar. TPSda semirish bilan bog'liq umumiy biologik yo'llarni aniqladi, bu sindromning patogenezida metabolik kasalliklarning muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. O'z navbatida, MJ ishi. Cox va boshqalar. sichqonlarda o'tkazilgan eksperimental modelda miya va yog' to'qimalari androgen bilan bog'liq reproduktiv disfunktsiyaning rivojlanishida asosiy rol o'ynashi ko'rsatilgan. Ushbu kashfiyot muhim klinik ta'sirga ega bo'lishi mumkin, chunki u endokrin va metabolik jihatlarni hisobga olgan holda TPSni davolashga kompleks yondashuv zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Bundan tashqari, qo'ylarda TPS modeli bo'yicha o'tkazilgan tadqiqot intranazal insulinni yuborish adaptiv termogenezni yaxshilashi mumkinligini ko'rsatdi, bu metabolik kasalliklarni tuzatish uchun yangi terapevtik yondashuvlar mavjudligini ko'rsatdi. Ushbu tadqiqotlar tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi uchun yanada samarali davolash usullarini ishlab chiqish uchun yangi ufqlarni ochadi va bu sohada keyingi tadqiqotlar muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Tuxumdon polikistoz sindromi ko'p qirrali kasallik bo'lib, uning patogenezini chuqur tushunishni va har bir bemorga individual yondashuvni talab qiladi. Jobira va boshqalar [8] ichak

mikrobiotasidagi zararli o'zgarishlar qandli diabet bilan og'rikan, semirib ketgan o'smirlarda ham mavjudligini aniqladilar. J. Guo [9] ning meta-tahlili, shuningdek, oshqozon-ichak mikrobiomasi va semirish, QD2 va PCOS kabi metabolik kasalliklar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni aniqladi. Biroq, ichak mikrobiotasi va tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromining individual ko'rinishlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik isbotlanmagan: TPS bilan og'rikan bemorlarda eng ko'p uchraydigan mikrobioma o'zgarishlari quyidagi mikrobiota bilan bog'liq: Bacteroides, Coprococcus, Bacteroides, Prevotella, Lactobacilluspp, Parabacteroides, Escherichiaspp/Shigellaspp va Fasciculi bacterium prausnitzii. Mikrobiomadagi o'zgarishlar TPSning oqibati yoki sababi ekanligini aniqlash uchun yuqori darajadagi dalillar talab qilinadi: Z. Liang va boshqalar tomonidan o'tkazilgan ovqatlanish tahlili [10] tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromi bilan klechatka va D vitamini iste'moli sezilarli darajada kamayganligini ko'rsatdi. Parabacteroides distasonis, Bacteroides fragilis va Escherichia coli, bu qon zardobidagi luteinlashtiruvchi gormon (LH) darajasi bilan ijobiy bog'liq edi. va LH va follikulani stimullovchi gormon nisbati (LH va follikullarni stimullovchi gormon (FSH) nisbati ijobiy bog'liq edi. Bochqach qilib aytganda, TPS bilan og'rikan ayollarda ichak disbiyozi, ehtimol, neyroendokrin o'zgarishlar bilan bog'liq; RV. Paris va boshqalar [11] eksperimental sichqoncha modelida nutrientlarning oziq-ovqat balansidagi o'zgarishlar metabolik ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sir qilmasdan reproduktiv imkoniyatlarini yaxshilashini ko'rsatib berdi; M. Besenek va boshqalar [12] giperandrogenemiya (qonda androgenlarning oshishi) nafaqat biokimyoviy ko'rsatkichlarga, balki bemorlarning ruhiy-psixologik holatiga ham ta'sir qilishi mumkinligini aytib o'tgan; L Tian va boshqalar [13] tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromi bilan og'rikan bemorlarda androgenga sezuvchan retseptorlari genida mutatsiyalarni (o'zgarishlarini) ko'rsatib berdi. Polikistik tuxumdon sindromi reproduktiv yoshdagi ayollarda keng o'rganilgan. Biroq, ko'proq tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, TPS ayollar salomatligining ko'p jihatlariga umrbod ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin: u menopauzaning qanday boshlanishi va kechishiga, shuningdek, menopauzadan oldin va keyin yurak-qon tomir tizimiga ta'sir qilishi mumkin. Shu jumladan, tuxumdon polikistozi sindromi ayolning ginekologik va boshqa onkologik o'smalarni paydo bo'lishi xavfini oshirishi mumkin; Tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromining xususiyatlari, ya'ni semirishning mavjudligi, testosteronning oshishi va jinsiy steroidlarni bog'laydigan globulin past darajasi yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari rivojlanishiga ta'sir qilishi mumkinligi ko'rsatilgan [15]. Bundan tashqari, hozirgi vaqtda tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromi bilan og'rikan ayollarda homiladorlikning ikkinchi trimestrining boshida testosterone gormoni ko'tarilib, preeklampsianing xavfini oshiradi [13]. Genetik moyillik va perinatal xavf omillarining mavjudligi ba'zi ayollarda TPS rivojlanish xavfini oshirishi haqida dalillar mavjud. Bu shuni anglatadiki, tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromi rivojlanish xavfi bilan bog'liq atrof-muhit omillari homila va chaqaloqqa bevosita yoki bilvosita onaning tanasi orqali ta'sir qiladi [14]. TPS poligen va multifaktorial sindrom buzilishi ekanligi isbotlangan; Tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromi bilan bog'liq ko'plab genlar to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yoki bilvosita unumdorlikka ta'sir qiladi TPS holatlarining 70% genetik omillar aniqlangan [1,4]; Tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromiga moyil bo'lgan genlarning roli FBN3, DENND1A, LHCGR, THADA, C9orf3, FSHR, HMGA2, INSR, RAB5B, SUMO 1P1, TOX3, YAP1ni o'z ichiga oladi. P450 sitoxrom P450 CYP11A1, CYP17A1 va CYP19A1 estrogenlari almashinuvi genlaridagi polimorfizmlar va Kreutzfeld-Jakob kasalligining rivojlanishi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik aniqlanmagan [2]. TPS ning sabab-ta'sir munosabatlari va rivojlanish mexanizmlarini baholash uchun foydali eksperimental modellarni ishlab chiqish uchun nomzod genlar, atrof-muhit va TPS chastotasi o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni aniqlashga qaratilgan fanlararo strategiya taklif qilindi [1,7]. So'nggi yillarda ushbu sindromning diagnostik mezonlarini aniqlash uchun ko'plab ma'lumotlar paydo bo'ldi. Gormonal jihatlar va insulin qarshiligi va semirish kabi metabolik kasalliklarga qo'shimcha ravishda, kutilganidan ertaroq glyukoza bardoshlilik rivojlanishiga moyillik, potentsial terapevtik strategiyalarni ishlab chiqish uchun ushbu jihatlarini diagnostika mezonlariga kiritish kerakligi ko'rib chiqiladi. Bundan tashqari, oilada va ayol va erkak qarindoshlarida PCOS ning oilaviy tarixi sindromning stigmatasini ko'rsatishi mumkin, bu genetik fonni ko'rsatadi [1]

Tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromi diagnostikasida yangiliklar

Hozirgi vaqtda tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromi diagnostikasi giperandrogenemiyaning klinik va laboratoriya belgilarini aniqlash, ultrasonografiya (LSI) yordamida hayz ko'rish va reproduktiv funktsiyani va tuxumdon morfologiyasini baholashga asoslangan [2]. 2018 yildan boshlab, ESHRE tavsiyalariga ko'ra, tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromining diagnostik mezonlari luteal tana, kistalar yoki dominant follikulalarning mavjudligi hisoblanadi. Bunday bo'lmasa, follikullar soni >20 va/yoki tuxumdonlar hajmi ≥ 10 sm³. har bir tuxumdonda 8 MGts chastotada transvaginal ultratovush yordamida aniqlanadi. Ushbu TPS diagnostikasi usulining sezgirligi va o'ziga xosligi mos ravishda 70,9% va 75,7% ni tashkil etdi [2,3]. Tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromini davolash maqsadlari androgenga bog'liq dermatoz belgilarini yo'qotishni o'z ichiga oladi. Ko'plab tadqiqot ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, Teede va boshqalar [2,5], ovulyatsiya induksiyasi reproduktiv rejalari bo'lmagan bemorlarni uzoq muddatli boshqarish uchun birinchi darajali terapiya sifatida ishlatilishi kerak. Ovulyatsiya induksiyasi homiladorlikni rejalashtirayotgan tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromi bilan og'rigan bemorlarda bepustlikni davolashning samarali usuli hisoblanadi [1,2]. Mustaqil ovulyatsiya uchun inositolni qabul qilish va yordamchi reproduktiv texnologiyalar kabi boshqa davolash usullaridan foydalanish mumkin [2,5]. Boshqa tadqiqot tavsiyalariga muvofiq girsutizmni davolash past dozali o'rin bosuvchi gormonal terapiya (shu jumladan antiandrogen ta'sirga ega neytral gestagenlar yoki gestagenlar), antiandrogenlar kuniga 50-100 mg dozada spironolakton kiritilgan [2.6]. Zamonaviy terapiyalarning hech biri tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromini to'liq davolay olmasligi sababli, davolashning asosiy strategiyasi umrbod terapiya bo'lib qolmoqda, garchi kasallik belgilariga muqobil ta'sir qilish usullarini izlash davom etmoqda [2,5]. O'simlik terapiyasining salohiyati o'rganildi [2,6,9], masalan turli vitamin qo'shimchalar [2,3,4]. Tuxumdonlarning laparoskopik drillingdan keyin tuxumdon polikiztozi sindromi bilan og'rigan bemorlarda Vitex agnus castus dan foydalanishning ijobiy tajribasi nashr etildi. Ushbu preparatni qabul qilish operatsiyadan keyingi davrda prolaktin darajasining oshishiga to'sqinlik qilishi va homiladorlik darajasini oshirishi mumkin [2,7]. Xuan lipid metabolizmini, jinsiy gormonlar sekretsiyasini va yallig'lanish reaksiyasini kamaytirishga yordam berdi, shuningdek, OATP2B1 va OATP3A1 ifodasini oshirdi [2,8]. Y. Xu va boshqalar [2,9] eksperimental modellarda adiponektin vositachiligidagi mexanizmlarni modulyatsiya qilish orqali FTZ retsepti (Xitoy tibbiyoti) Kreutzfeld-Jakob kasalligi rivojlanishining oldini olish qobiliyatini namoyish etganligini aniqladilar. Bir tadqiqotda [3] doljin qo'shilishi TPS bo'lgan ayollarda insulin qarshiligini (HOMA-IR) sezilarli darajada kamaytirdi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, doljinni iste'mol qilish insulin qarshiligi uchun xavfsiz va foydali tavsiya hisoblanadi [3]. Hozirgi vaqtda TPS bilan og'rigan ayollarda koenzim Q10 ning lipid profiliga va yallig'lanish biomarkerlariga ta'sirini baholovchi tadqiqotlar o'z ifodasini topgan [3,4]. Koenzim Q10, yog'da eriydigan tabiiy vitamin, oksidlanish va qaytarilish davrlaridan o'tadi, samarali antioksidant bo'lib, tuxumdonlarni oksidlovchi stressdan himoya qilishi mumkin. Simvastatin va metformin bilan kombinatsiyalangan terapiya bo'yicha tadqiqot nashr etildi. Ushbu kombinatsiya TPSni davolashda metformindan ko'ra samaraliroq ekanligi ko'rsatildi, bu umumiy testosteron, LH/FSH va xolesterin nisbatining sezilarli darajada pasayishi aniqlangan [3,5]. Klinik homiladorlik va ovulyatsiya darajasi klomifen sitrat va metformin kombinatsiyasini olgan bemorlarda faqat klomifen sitrat olganlarga qaraganda yuqori bo'lgan, ammo kombinatsiyalangan davolash tirik tug'ilganlar sonini oshiradimi yoki yo'qmi noma'lum. Ushbu meta-tahlil D-xironositol (DCI) samaradorligini o'rganuvchi ikkita tadqiqotni o'z ichiga oladi, ammo mualliflar tahlil qilingan ayollar soni mavjud ma'lumotlarga asoslanib xulosa chiqarish uchun juda oz degan xulosaga kelishdi [3,7]. Tahlil TPS bilan kasallangan 1472 bepust ayolni o'z ichiga oldi. TPS bilan kasallangan 1472 bepust ayolni o'z ichiga olgan 13 ta tadqiqotning meta-tahlili ham inositolning klinik homiladorlik va tirik tug'ilish chastotasini oshirishda samaradorligini ko'rsatmadi [3,8]. TPS bilan og'rigan bemorlarda inositolning samaradorligi to'g'risida ishonchli ma'lumotlar hali olinmagan. Biroq, so'nggi bir necha yil ichida adabiyotda inositolning ikkala shaklining samaradorligi to'g'risida ma'lumotlar to'plangan [40-50]. Miyoinositol (MI) va DSI insulinning ikkilamchi vositachilari bo'lib, FSH ishlab chiqarishda ishtirok etadi va ovulyatsiya jarayonini tartibga soladi. Mi/dci ning to'qimalarga xos nisbati aromataza orqali insulin tomonidan modulyatsiya qilinadi va insulinga sezgir to'qimalarda DCIda MI epimerizatsiyasini kamaytirish orqali insulin qarshiligida o'zgaradi. So'nggi yillarda inositol (MI va DCI) TPSni

davolashda samarali va xavfsiz alternativ ekanligi ko'rsatildi, chunki DCI asosan tuxumdondan tashqarida insulin faolligini rag'batlantiradi, Inozitol TPSda samarali ekanligini ko'rsatdi, metabolizm va gormonlar darajasini yaxshiladi va o'z-o'zidan ovulyatsiyani tikladi [4].

Insulinrezistentlik - bu insulinning maqsadli hujayralar tomonidan glyukoza so'rilishini rag'batlantirish qobiliyatining pasayishi bilan tavsiflangan patologik holat bo'lib, bu qon zardobidagi insulin kontsentratsiyasining oshishiga va insulin sintezining kompesator o'sishiga olib keladi [4, 5]. [5-7]. Turli manbalarga ko'ra, TPS bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 30-90 foizida LH darajasi oshadi va 65-75 foizida akne, girsutizm va alopesiya kabi giperandrogenizm belgilari rivojlanadi [8,9]. Shu bilan birga, boshqa organlar va to'qimalardan tuxumdondan insulinga normal sezgirlikni saqlaydi, bu «tuxumdondan paradoksi» [10] deb ataladi. [6, 10]. Shunday qilib, tizimli IR va GI bilan tuxumdondan ortiqcha insulinga ta'sir qiladi, bu oosit granuloza hujayralarining FSHga sezgirlikni pasaytiradi va LH darajasining oshishi bilan follikullar shakllanishini bostiradi [11, 12]. Bundan tashqari, insulin darajasining oshishi follikulada LH retseptorlari ifodasini tezlashtirmaydi va granuloza hujayralarining erta terminal differentsiatsiyasiga va oositlarning kamolotining turg'unligiga olib kelishi mumkin [13].

Insulin to'g'ridan-to'g'ri steroidogenezga ta'sir qilishi, xususan, androgen sintezini qo'zg'atishi va gonadotropinlar sekretsiyasini o'zgartirmasdan jinsiy gormonlarni bog'laydigan globulin darajasini kamaytirishi ko'rsatilgan. Gonadotropinlar, follikul retseptorlari apparati va giperandrogenemiya sekretsiyasining buzilishi insulin qarshiligi tufayli anovulyatsiya, oligomenoreya yoki amenoreya va bepushtlikka olib keladi [11-13]. Biroq, fan rivojlanishining ushbu bosqichida IR diagnostikasi unchalik aniq emas.

Uni baholashning yagona to'g'ridan-to'g'ri usuli - bu giperinsulinemik anemiya bilan klemp testi bo'lib, uni bajarish qiyin va klinik amaliyotda qo'llanilmaydi. Eng keng tarqalgan bilvosita usullar glyukoza bardoshlik testi va HOMA indeksidir. Adabiyotlarga ko'ra, IR TPS bilan og'rigan ayollarning taxminan 50-70 foizida mavjud va semirish mavjud bo'lganda, IR tarqalishi 95% gacha oshadi. Biroq, mavjud diagnostika usullarining to'liq emasligi sababli IR ning haqiqiy tarqalishi yuqori bo'lishi mumkin [14-15]. Clamp tadqiqotiga ko'ra, TPS bilan og'rigan bemorlarda insulin sezgirligi sog'lom ayollarga nisbatan 27% ga past bo'lgan va tana massasi indeksi (BMI) [16] bilan sezilarli bog'liqlik aniqlanmagan, bu bemorlarning 86,6% gacha ta'sir qilishi mumkin [14, 15]. Insulin qarshiligi lipid almashinuvi va uglevod almashinuvining buzilishi bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, bu ayniqsa ko'pincha visseral yog 'massasining oshishiga olib keladi. Shunday qilib, TPS bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 30-70% ortiqcha vazn va semirishga ega [13, 15] va 40 yoshgacha bo'lgan har

ikkinchi bemorda metabolik sindrom (MS) yoki 2-toifa qandli diabet (QD2) [1] rivojlanishi mumkin. Mualliflar ortiqcha yog' to'qimalari hatto normal tana massasi indeksida (BMI) mavjud bo'lganda, yashirin semirishning yuqori tarqalishini ta'kidladilar. Tadqiqotga ko'ra, TMI 23 kg/m² yoki undan ko'p bo'lgan odamlar yashirin semirish xavfi ostida [2]. Shunisi e'tiborga loyiqki, bu metabolik faol va nosog'lom visseral yog' to'qimalarining massasi va ulushini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Visseral yog' to'qimalari va ko'p skleroz o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik yaxshi ma'lum, chunki visseral yog' to'qimalari lipid va endokrin metabolizmning buzilishiga, yallig'lanish vositachilarining sekretiysiga va tizimli yallig'lanishga olib keladi [2].

Ma'lumki, glyukoza almashinuvining buzilishi va semirish oksidlovchi stress, yallig'lanish, jigarda erkin yog' kislotalari (SFA) va triglitseridlar (TG) to'planishi va oxir-oqibat alkogolsiz yog'li jigar kasalligi (NAFLD) jigar hujayralari tomonidan yog' to'qimalarining to'planishi holati rivojlanishi bilan chambarchas bog'liq. NAFLD bilan yog' to'qimalarida lipoliz kuchayadi va jigarda yog' kislotalarining b-oksidlanishi kamayadi, bu esa gipertrigliceridemiya, giperqlikemiya olib keladi.

Xulosa qilib shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, TPSda IR ning asl sababi noaniq bo'lib qolmoqda; IR endogendir, ammo semirish mavjudligida rivojlanadi deb ishoniladi [8]. Kasallikning patogenezinining murakkabligini hisobga olgan holda, simptomatik davolash, ayniqsa kombinatsiyalangan oral kontratseptsiyasi, ovulyatsiyani rag'batlantirish terapiyasi va yordamchi reproduktiv texnologiyalar dasturi (YRT) klinik ko'rsatmalarga muvofiq davolashning birinchi qatori bo'lib qolmoqda [2,3]. Patogenetik davolash usullarini ishlab chiqish tadqiqotning ustuvor yo'nalishi bo'lib qolmoqda; IR ning muhim rolini hisobga olgan holda, bemorlarini boshqarish protokollari insulin sensitizerlarini, xususan, tsiklni tartibga solishda samaradorligi atigi 27-53% bo'lgan eng ko'p o'rganilgan vakil metforminni ham o'z ichiga oladi [2,8]. F. Fruzzetti va boshqalar [4,5] TPS va oligomenoreya bilan og'rigan 57 ayolda a-lipoik kislota va MI (kuniga 2000 mg + 800 mg) bilan kombinatsiyalangan davolash samaradorligini baholadilar. Tadqiqot TPS va oligomenoreya bilan og'rigan 57 ayolda o'tkazildi. Umuman olganda, kombinatsiya TPS bilan og'rigan ayollar uchun uzoq muddatli davolanish sifatida foydali bo'lib, hayz ko'rish va insulin darajasini normallashtirdi olib keldi; Merviel va boshqalar [4] tuxumdon stimulyatsiyasidan uch oy oldin kuniga 4 g MI (kuniga ikki marta 2 g) qabul qilish tuxumdonlar faoliyatini normallashtirgani va tuxum va embrion sifatini yaxshilagani haqida xabar berdi. Bundan tashqari, MI TPS uchun xavfsiz va tejamkor davolash usuli bo'lib, standart dozalarda nojo'ya ta'sirlar kuzatilmagan. Shunday qilib, adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish TPS

patogenezi bo'yicha qarashlarning o'zgarishini, ushbu kasallikni davolashda yangi yo'nalishlarning paydo bo'lishini va dalillar bazasining o'sib borayotganini ko'rsatadi. Inositol hayz ko'rish va reproduktiv funktsiyani normallashtirishga yordam beradi, ehtimol uglevod va lipid metabolizmiga ta'sir qiladi, tuxum va embrionlarning sifatini yaxshilaydi.

REFERENCES | СНОСКИ | IQTIBOSLAR:

1. Али Р. М. и др. Генетические ассоциации между полиморфными локусов генов ферментов антиоксидантной защиты GPX4 (rs713041), GSTP1 (rs1695) и PON1 (rs662) и синдромом поликистозных яичников у российских женщин //Медицинская генетика. – 2024. – Т. 23. – №. 3. – С. 21-30.;
2. Dumesic DA, Abbott DH, Chazenbalk GD. An Evolutionary Model for the Ancient Origins of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome. *J Clin Med.* 2023 Sep 22;12(19):6120. doi: 10.3390/jcm12196120. PMID: 37834765; PMCID: PMC10573644
3. Гасиева Д. М. и др. Синдром поликистозных яичников: новые и перспективные варианты лечения //Problems of Endocrinology. – 2024. – Т. 70. – №. 4. – С. 103
4. Joham A.E., Norman R.J., Stener-Victorin E. et al. Polycystic ovary syndrome. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol.* 2022;10(9):668–680. DOI: 10.1016/S2213-8587(22)00163-2.
5. Unluhizarci K., Karaca Z., Kelestimur F. Role of insulin and insulin resistance in androgen excess disorders. *World J Diabetes.* 2021;12(5):616–629. DOI: 10.4239/wjd.v12.i5.616.
6. Moghetti P., Tosi F. Insulin resistance and PCOS: chicken or egg? *J Endocrinol Invest.* 2021;44(2):233–244. DOI: 10.1007/s40618-020-01351-0.
7. Kamenov Z., Gateva A. Inositols in PCOS. *Molecules.* 2020;25(23):5566. DOI: 10.3390/molecules25235566.
8. Siddiqui S. et al. A brief insight into the etiology, genetics, and immunology of polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) //Journal of assisted reproduction and genetics. – 2022. – Т. 39. – №. 11. – С. 2439-2473.;
9. Рахимов Н. М. и др. ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ АСЦИТА ОБУСЛОВЛЕННЫЙ РЕЦИДИВОМ ПЛАТИНОРЕФРАКТЕРНОГО РАКА ЯИЧНИКА С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ МЕТРОНОМНОЙ ХИМИОТЕРАПИИ //ЖУРНАЛ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ И УРО-НЕФРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 1.
10. Abdurakhmonov Jurabek , Rahimov Nodir , Shakhanova Shakhnoza . Modern view on ascite in ovarian cancer. *Journal of Biomedicine and Practice .* 2022, vol . 7, issue 4, pp . 130-139
11. Alimjanovich JR, Agababyan LR, Kamalov AI Prevention and Treatment of Postpartum Hemorrhage //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – S. 204-209.
12. Rizaev Jasur , Rakhimov Nodir , Kodyrov Khamidullo , Shakhanova Shakhnoza . Study of prostate cancer death by regions of the republic of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Biomedicine and Practice.* 2022, vol . 7, issue 5, pp.202-210
13. Carlomagno G., Unfer V., Roseff S. The D-chiro-inositol paradox in the ovary. *Fertil Steril.* 2011;95(8):2515–2516. DOI: 10.1016/j.fertnstert.2011.05.027.
14. De Leo V., Musacchio M.C., Cappelli V. et al. Genetic, hormonal and metabolic aspects of PCOS: an update. *Reprod Biol Endocrinol.* 2016;14(1):38. DOI: 10.1186/s12958-016-0173-x.
15. Behboudi-Gandevani S., Ramezani Tehrani F., Rostami Dovom M. et al. Insulin resistance in obesity and polycystic ovary syndrome: systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *Gynecol Endocrinol.* 2016;32(5):343–353. DOI: 10.3109/09513590.2015.1117069.
16. Guarano A., Capozzi A., Cristodoro M. et al. Alpha Lipoic Acid Efficacy in PCOS Treatment: What Is the Truth? *Nutrients.* 2023;15(14):3209. DOI: 10.3390/nu15143209.

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10 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 10, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 10, ISSUE 1

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